

Effect of In-Plane Thermal Conduction on Thermoelastic Stress Measurement of Laminate Composites with Stress Concentration

Sunao Sugimoto^{*}, Takashi Ishikawa^{*}, Robert E. Rowlands[#]

^{*}: *Advanced Composite Center, National Aerospace Laboratory of Japan,
6-13-1 Ohsawa, Mitaka, Tokyo 181-0015, Japan*

[#]: *Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Wisconsin, Madison*

ABSTRACT: Thermoelastic stress measurement is a useful non-destructive evaluation technique. There is, however, thermal conduction from inner layer(s) and/or in-plane of surface layer, which affects thermoelastic stress measurement. The main reason of this is each layer has different quantity of heat caused by thermoelastic effect and stress concentration region also has different quantity of heat from general region. So, this thermal conduction should be examined to make sure the meaning of the measured data. Two-dimensional finite element analysis (FEA) has been conducted for evaluating this thermal conductive effect with no stress concentration model in the previous works. The FEA result was compared with experimental result and they agreed with each other. In this paper, effect of in-plane thermal conduction on thermoelastic stress measurement of laminate composites with stress concentration is discussed with two-dimensional FEA and experiment. The FEA and experiment results were conducted for two laminate composites, carbon/epoxy system and stacking sequences of type A, (45/-45/0/90)_s, and type B, (0/90/45/-45)_s. These laminates have an open hole in the center because the exact stress distribution can be easily calculated. Type A is mainly discussed in this paper, since quasi-isotropic laminates of 45 surface layer is commonly used. Stresses from both FEA and experiment results were obtained at the intersection point between open hole edge and a line that is normal to load and includes hole center under various load frequencies. The experimental values are similar to the FEA values. Consequently, thermoelastic stress measurement technique can be applicable to quantitative stress measurement for quasi-isotropic laminate composites of 45 surface layer with attention to the peak value drop. In the case of quasi-isotropic laminates with 0 surface layer, the result of thermoelastic stress measurement is mainly ruled by the heat conduction from inner layers more than stress concentration at 5 Hz of load frequency.

KEYWORDS: Thermoelastic stress measurement, Thermal conduction, FEA, Stress concentration

INTRODUCTION

A solid body shows a thermoelastic temperature change caused by a load change under adiabatic condition, similarly in mechanism but too much less extent than gaseous body. By utilizing this phenomenon, thermoelastic stress measurement technique was established. This technique provides the sum of principle stress changes in the surface of isotropic solid body through a temperature measurement corresponding to a load change by using infrared thermo-camera. A cyclic load is required for an accumulation of data to improve S/N ratio in temperature change data. The thermoelastic stress measurement takes only reversible stress amplitude in principle. Finally, the temperature amplitude is converted to stress using thermoelastic constants. So, effect of viscoelasticity and internal friction are not taken into account in measuring temperature data.

In the case of CFRP laminates, however, thermal conduction from inner layer (out-of-plane) and in-plane conduction can be occurred, affecting thermoelastic stress measurement, because each layer shows different generated heat by thermoelasticity or because stress concentration generates more heat than general stress region. So, this thermal conduction should be examined to make sure the meaning of measured data. The heat conduction effect on thermoelastic stress measurement from inner layer had been examined with experiment and finite element analysis (FEA) by the authors ^[1].

^[2]. In this paper, open hole specimens were tested with thermoelastic stress measurement and compared with FEA results to study the heat conduction effect of stress concentration in plane.

BASIS OF THERMOELASTIC STRESS MEASUREMENT APPLIED TO LAMINATE COMPOSITES

In the case of unidirectional CFRP (UD-CFRP), thermoelastic stress analysis must be examined with consideration to its orthotropic properties. A theoretical basis of thermoelastic stress measurement applied to UD-CFRP is reviewed in this section.

A temperature change caused by thermoelasticity can be described in the following equation as demonstrated by Kageyama et al. ^{[3],[4]}.

$$dT = -\frac{T}{\rho \cdot C_\sigma} (\alpha_L \cdot d\sigma_L + \alpha_T \cdot d\sigma_T) \quad (1)$$

where dT is a temperature amplitude, T is an environmental temperature (the absolute in Kelvin), ρ is a density, C_σ is a specific heat at constant stress, α is a thermal expansion and $d\sigma$ is a stress amplitude. In this paper, subscripts, L and T , indicate the fiber and transverse directions respectively. By substituting the following equations into Equation (1), we have

$$K_L = \frac{\alpha_L}{\rho \cdot C_\sigma} \quad (2)$$

$$K_T = \frac{\alpha_T}{\rho \cdot C_\sigma} \quad (3)$$

It can be rewritten as follows:

$$dT = -T(K_L \cdot d\sigma_L + K_T \cdot d\sigma_T) \quad (4)$$

These K 's (in Equations (2) and (3)) are referred to as the thermoelastic constants.

In the case of CFRP, a thermoelastic constant in the fiber direction is, however, much smaller than the transverse constant, that is $|K_L| \ll |K_T|$, and so a temperature amplitude caused by load in the fiber direction is also much smaller than the transverse temperature amplitude. Therefore measured temperature amplitude can be ruled by stress amplitude in the transverse direction, if the fiber angle is enough away from 0. In this situation, Equation (4) can be approximated by the next equation.

$$dT \cong -K_T \cdot T \cdot d\sigma_T \quad (5)$$

The stresses on orthotropic elastic axes, $d\sigma_T$ and $d\sigma_L$, are respectively zero in 0 and 90 UD-CFRP under uniaxial loads to 0 and 90. So, the thermoelastic constants of UD-CFRP, K_L and K_T , are easily obtained from experimental data and Equation (1) without any approximation. The following thermoelastic constants ^[5] are obtained in this procedure with UD-CF/Epoxy laminates.

$$K_L = -1.21 \times 10^{-13} [\text{1/Pa}] \quad (6)$$

$$K_T = 2.30 \times 10^{-11} [\text{1/Pa}] \quad (7)$$

These values are used in FEA in this paper.

From Equation (6) and (7), it is very clear that generated heat amplitude caused by the transverse stress is much higher than the amplitude in the fiber direction. So, the generated heat amplitudes are different in each layer of multi-directional laminates. On the other hand, it is very difficult to maintain adiabatic conditions between layers due to upper frequency limit in the present tests of 30 Hz. Therefore, thermal conduction between layers may occur and the heat flux from inner layers to the surface has the same frequency as generated heat. This thermal conduction between layers has been examined in the previous work ^{[1],[2]}. It had been obtained that there is not much impact of heat conduction effect from inner layer on thermoelastic stress measurement for quasi-isotropic laminates with 45 surface layer. In the case of 0 surface layer, however, the result of thermoelastic stress measurement is affected by heat conduction from inner layers.

THERMOELASTIC STRESS MEASUREMENT

Specimens and Test Machine

In order to examine heat conduction effect of stress concentration in plane, two types of laminate composites were measured by thermoelastic stress measurement system. These composite systems were consisted of carbon/epoxy and stacking sequences of type A, $(45/-45/0/90)_s$, and type B, $(0/90/45/-45)_s$. The specimens were 25 X 220 mm size, bonded tapered tabs on the gripped area and opened a hole of $\phi 3.0$ mm in the specimen center. The main interest is how stress concentration affects thermoelastic stress measurement. In this point of view, existing specimens but not enough for infinite plate in width was used here for the test. The both types have three specimens. All specimens were coated with black paint that has emissivity value of 0.96 for enhancement of it. Thermoelastic stress analysis system, JTG-8000 by JEOL Co., Ltd. and hydraulic fatigue testing machine, Instron type 8802, of 100 kN capacity were used here. Loading conditions were tension-tension with maximum load of 100 MPa, 0.1 stress ratio and 5Hz sine wave. It should be also noted that a phase shift between stress peak and temperature bottom happens usually although an elementary theory tells us no phase shift. From the viewpoint of hardware, this system uses the feedback of the loading signals to determine the measurement timing. For the determining the actual phase shift, some preliminary trial is needed.

Experiments and Its Results

Applied stress amplitude, 90 MPa, was enough low not to make damages. This means stress distribution pattern had not changed during measurement. A measured region that contains an open hole is illustrated in Figure 1. In this thermoelastic stress measurement system, JTG-8000, maximum and minimum peak temperatures are measured and accumulated respectively to improve S/N ratio and then temperature amplitude distribution pattern corresponding to the stress amplitude distribution is obtained as a difference between these peak temperature patterns. The position of every point in one peak temperature pattern must be corrected with the other one peak temperature pattern because of the deformation.

A typical result of type A is shown in Figure 2, Figure 3 and 4 shows typical temperature amplitude distribution graph of type A and B along the line normal to load direction and including hole center. A comparison between Figure 3 and 4 give us that the maximum stress values at the hole edge are not much different. This result is same as the prediction demonstrated in Reference [1] by the authors. If the adiabatic condition is achieved, the temperature amplitude at the hole edge in Figure 4 must be much smaller because thermoelastic constant in 0 layer is very small that mentioned above. Temperature amplitudes with type A and B laminates were similarly measured under load frequency of 1, 5, 10, 15 and 20 Hz. Measured results of three specimens are averaged and shown in Figure 5. It is very clear that type A is insensitive to load frequency but type B is sensitive to it.

Figure 3 Measured temperature amplitude distribution for type A laminates.

Figure 4 Measured temperature amplitude distribution for type B laminates.

Figure 5 Comparison of temperature amplitudes of experimental results at the intersection point between open hole edge and a line that is normal to load and includes hole center for type A and B laminates.

COMPARISON WITH FEA RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two-dimensional 8-node element in FEA code ANSYS was employed in this calculation and this FEA model was corresponding to experiment mentioned above. The calculated temperature results of heat transfer FEA for type A laminates with load frequency of 5 and 20 Hz is shown in Figure 6. A theoretical result that means adiabatic condition is also plotted in Figure 6. This FEA model was a quarter of the actual laminate section normal to load direction and including the hole center because of its symmetry. Figure 6 indicates that there is no much difference between temperature amplitude for 5 and 20 Hz calculated by FEA in the general region. Therefore there is almost no impact of heat transfer from stress concentration region and inner layers on the stress measurement in general stress region.

The peak values of temperature amplitude for 5 and 20 Hz are different at the hole edge and they are in proportion to the load frequency. These FEA peak values are shown in Figure 7 with experiment results shown in Figure 5. The higher load frequency can improve the inadequate adiabatic condition. The values of FEA at 5 and 20 Hz are about 80 and 90 % of theoretical (adiabatic condition) value. The experimental values are similar to the FEA values but little bigger than the FEA. The reason of this is possibly considered as error in assumptions of FEA model and/or tolerances in the test. Type A does not have clear dependency on load frequency and this is a merit for quantitative measurement. Therefore thermoelastic stress measurement technique is usefully applicable quantitative stress measurement for 45 surface quasi-isotropic laminate composites with attention to this peak value drop. In the case of 0 surface layer, the peak value at the hole edge must be very small under the adiabatic condition. It is not very small and almost same level as 45 surface laminates. The heat conduction from inner layers mainly controls the thermoelastic stress measurement in the case of load frequency 5 Hz. So, the thermoelastic stress measurement of 0 surface quasi-isotropic laminate composites must be carefully examined.

Figure 6 Calculated temperature amplitude distributions by FEA along the line normal to load direction and including hole center for type A laminates, (45/-45/0/90)s , vs. load frequency.

Figure 7 Comparison of temperature amplitudes between experimental and FEA results at the intersection point between open hole edge and a line that is normal to load and includes hole center for type A laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

The thermal conductive effect from stress concentration to thermoelastic stress measurement was examined here with experimental and finite element analysis data. Consequently, thermoelastic stress measurement technique can be applicable to quantitative stress measurement for laminate composites that is quasi-isotropic laminates and 45 surface layer. Only the attention on the peak value drop must be paid in the case of 45 surface layer. However the result of thermoelastic stress measurement of quasi-isotropic laminates with 0 surface layer is mainly ruled by the heat conduction from inner layers more than stress concentration at 5 Hz of load frequency.

REFERENCES

1. Sunao Sugimoto, Takashi Ishikawa. 1999. "Numerical Analysis of heat conduction effect corresponding to infrared stress measurements in multi-lamina CFRP Plates," *Advanced Composite Materials.*, 8(3):269-279.
2. S. Sugimoto, R.E. Rowlands and T. Ishikawa, "A Thermal Conductivity Analysis Affecting Thermoelastic Stress Measurement of Laminate", Proceedings of ICCM-13, 2001.
3. Kazuo Kageyama. 1989. "Application of Infrared Stress Graphic System for FRP (translated from Japanese)," *Materials Science.*, 26(1):16-21, (in Japanese).
4. Kazuo Kageyama, Kiyoshi Ueki and Masaki Kikuchi. 1989. "Thermoelastic Technique Applied to Stress Analysis of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Composite Materials," *6th International Congress Experimental Mechanics*, pp. 931-936.
5. Sunao Sugimoto, Takashi Ishikawa. 1997. "Examination of Thermo-Elastic Constants of UD-CFRP Composites as the Basis of Infrared Stress Measurements," *Journal of the Japan Society for Composite Material*, 23(1):7-14, (in Japanese).